

The legal capability thought and its application at the Civil law

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Abstract

The reason for composing a public theory of the legal ability is to reveal the common rules, that all its dispersed applications contribute to all civil law's items. The ability with its different applications has one origin, determination and one foundation. The importance of composing one public theory relied on many legal patterns, many options and the granting given by law to specific persons regarding their positions, and they can be called the legal abilities, which made us confronting responsibility in presenting answers for the questions that will be asked: What we mean by legal ability? What is its statutory basic? What are its conditions, content and applications at the civil legislation? And many other general questions. Regarding this study, all the questions will be answered.

Keywords: Legal capability, Gifted, Benefactor, civil law, Freedom, Right.

1-The essence of this paper

The "Right" terminology is considered one of the common use, but the legal Jurisprudence with a long history of qualification and identification and however of the serious and repeated tries no one succeeded to remove the ambiguity at some of its aspects methodically to achieve the target.

The problem has emerged, when Jurisprudence have seen the concept of truth had combined with other different concepts and distinctive in many essential important issues and almost freedom lost among them and the legal capabilities. The result was many concepts had been combined. Some Jurisprudents distinguished between freedom and permit to correspond between them by using the legal abilities, and the result was a kind of Jurisprudence immobility in processing the legal abilities. The result was the match of capability and freedom, the right and the middle grade between them from the other side. The truth expelled the three concepts of correspondence; Freedom, legal capability and right.

2-The Research Problem

The problem of this paper highlights the combination of the three concepts while determining the terminologies concepts in law is considered one of the important objects which is linked directly to the legal base application, legal adoption of the cases that presented to the courthouse and in determining the legal different positions in law. Nonetheless, presenting the problem to be processed from the side of Jurisprudence, the courthouse and legitimately was neglected, and the legal capability was named in a different name, once they called it the right, the freedom or the permit, the desecrate and the middle grade between the right and the freedom. However, the legal capability is considered as an independent legal status. So, the position is going to be different for the capability than the right and the freedom. Instead, there is no general theory in the Jurisprudence books, researchers and specialists that collect the elements and the features of the legal capability.

3-Search Scope

The application of legal capabilities is prevailed in all law branches, whether at the private or public law. But, the research size was exclusively at civil law regarding the numerous applications. Instead, civil law represents general legislation including its branches. It organizes the different general patterns theories. The process will be made in two patterns: the first one is

the general theory pattern, and the second pattern is the presentation of legal applications of this theory.

4-Research Methodology

The analytical and Applied methodology have followed, starting with the related terminologies. Some of the Egyptian civil law attitude beside the Iraqi civil law in some capability applications. This study is not comparative due to its benefit on this subject. The most important thing is to analyze this thought, that no one before had analyzed it on the part of Methodologically, theoretically and practically as we know.

5-Research structure

The research has divided into two sections; the first one has entitled " The establishing of the origin of legal capability and its concept, and this section has divided into three requests, the first one is the thought stability stages at the legal thought and old legislations, the second request is the concept of the legal capability and elements and the third one is distinguishing the legal capability as the suspected status.

The second section has entitled " The legal capability applications, which has been divided into two requests: the first one is the capabilities used at the real rights field and the second request at the personal rights field. This paper has ended with conclusions and recommendations.

6-The first section

6-1 The origin of legal capability and its concept

In order to clarify the legal capability thought concept, we have to establish the origin of this thought and analyzing it, so we have divided this section into three requests:

A. The thought stability stages at the legal thought and old legislations.

The right is a legal position that gives the will capability with a commitment by another person, it means that the right creates different legal centers between the right holder and the one who uses the right to confront him⁽¹²⁾. Besides, there are the legal position that will and capability can be given, or the capability of establishing new positions, or amending or removing previous centers. For example, during the contracting session, the selection will be among acceptance and refusal, and if the selection is the first one the legal position will be created and applied to all without asking to do a certain act or refuse. The question is, It is possible to make both previous positions similar as we indicated before? Can we reach the scientific result in the case of analyzing the legal relationship between the two parties in the previous example? Then who directed with pollicitation in a position allows him the capability of using acceptance or refusal option, he can't be designated for the first and the second position in the accurate meaning for the word "The right", but the resultant of this analysis is the legal creative capability existence for new rights or amended or necessary for standing rights that are different from the essence of right and character. The first signs of this analysis and distinguishing at the legal Jurisprudence appeared at the German, Swiss and Italian Jurisprudence then transferred to the French Jurisprudence⁽³⁾.

The German Jurisprudent (Beaker) discussed the legal capability existence and the causes of the removal of the legal position or previous existed standing rights were called negative rights. While the German Jurisprudent (Anis Ross) remarked the legal capability existence that causes new rights acquisition called the rights of acquisition, and Seagle Wits Yaltman tried to combine the two previous classes, and the called them the Creative right or the possibility right or the legal possibility right⁽⁴⁾. The most remarkable thing, that all these Jurisprudents used the word "The right", and this new class has the legal capability and it is one of the classes of right, but it is a legal capability and it is linguistically and terminology "Rights" for the word " the right". That what we will explain later. Jusran, the French Jurisprudent also discussed the legal capability thought and called it "Uncaused rights" when referred to the privileges made by the legislator. He referred to the capabilities that are legally admitted to the owner in neighborly

relations. He added also, the father's rights in their sons' marriages, and he added the freedom of not marrying, which is a kind of combination among the freedom and capability⁽⁵⁾.

The issues that have been discussed represent Jurisprudence opinions and attitudes, and those Jurisprudents realized of legal capabilities existence represented in freedom and the right, and they expressed these two words with different useless expressions, that didn't signify the meaning and essence of the legal capability. Instead, the legal capabilities were discussed at the ancient legal legislations without discussing the name and oneself, but only in legal regulations and articles. Hammurabi codex includes a group of regulations that award legal capabilities to those subservient to the legal articles that are related to marriage and divorces. The marriage system origin at this legislation is an individual marriage system, which means having one single legal wife⁽⁶⁾. But these details were amended with some exceptions represented in polygamy and concubinage⁽⁷⁾. Regarding polygamy, this legislation stipulated in private cases gave the man the legal capability to marry from a second wife or divorcing them with the first wife subordination based on the husband's decision under the law. One of these cases is the wife's misbehavior⁽⁸⁾, and if the wife was sick with the dangerous disease⁽⁹⁾, and if the wife hated her husband greatly. She has the right to return to her father's house in case of some conditions are presented⁽¹⁰⁾.

While at the Arabic legal Jurisprudence, stability in interpretation is remarkable or they agreed on specific terminology. Some of them named it " The Voluntary Right", but later they called it "The legal Capability Right or the Legal Capability". Some of them used the term "The Optional Right"⁽¹¹⁾.

B. The Legal Capability concept and Elements

At this request we process the legal capability, then we determine the legal capability elements.

B.1 The legal capability concept determination

We will try to devise the legal capability concept, and through this, we can find a terminological definition that meets the requirement. The word "Capability" may mean the place or the status "1" as mentioned in the Holy Qur'an (A similar place"⁽¹²⁾, or "And when they threw in a narrow place". But, many Verses are referring to the meaning of the Capability or the Ability "To establish a firm place to them"⁽¹³⁾, and " that He will establish in authority their religion - the one which He has chosen for them"⁽¹⁴⁾.

But some linguists argued that place denotation just for expansion because capability means to be able. Some say, "that a certain person has a great status to the king ", and some say " A certain person has great status among his people"⁽¹⁵⁾. Almighty Allah said "Who is possessed of power and with the Owner of the Throne, secure [in position]"⁽¹⁶⁾, it means he enabled a certain person, things became easy to him, the status and betterment⁽¹⁷⁾. We can say also, enabled him and made things possible as in Almighty Allah's words "It is We Who have placed you with authority on earth"⁽¹⁸⁾, "We had established them in a manner We have not established you"⁽¹⁹⁾. Regarding Terminology, the French Jurisprudence had used a word referring to the capability (Faculte), the Italian Jurisprudence had used the word (Facolta) and the German Jurisprudence used (Rechderecht Lichen Konnens) and the phrases of Negative Rights, The Creative Rights, Possibility Right, The Legal Possibility Right or the Fatalism Rights⁽²⁰⁾. The legal Arab Jurisprudence used the legal capability terminology to refer to " Voluntary Rights"⁽²¹⁾, (The Optional Right"⁽²²⁾, "The permission Rights"⁽²³⁾, "The Middle status", "The Creative Right"⁽²⁴⁾, "The Possibility Right or The Capability Right). While the Arab Legislators used "Permission" as a denotation⁽²⁵⁾.

Regarding the mentioned above, the Legal and legislative Jurisprudence had used the denotation of the legal capability thought according to each aspect seen by different Jurisprudents. And the Jurisprudence had never selected a specific concept that gathers all the elements of the thought constitution and its legal foundation.

Since the capability is defined in language as the ability or been able, and in the legal terminology it was defined in many ways, and we are trying to display some of them, analyzing them and explaining their concept. The German Foon Toor is defined as the person's capability to build a private legal position and making a legal impact alone⁽²⁶⁾. The legal capability regarding this definition is represented in its elements; the will "A private legal position allows the will holder to create a new legal position, or amending them or removing standing legal positions, obeying and others submitted to the legal consequences that occurred by the will holder."⁽²⁷⁾

Kabitan defined the legal capability as the " The admitted Right to the individual to commence or not commence some activities which are legal and protecting them against any aggression from others"⁽²⁸⁾. This definition identified The Capability of others (The Right), which means out of its essence. Also, the definition combines Capability and Freedom, and both concepts cannot be correspondent due to the lack of similarities. Some of the Jurisprudents defined the capability as the feature of the Right but not the Right itself⁽²⁹⁾. The permission is also defined as " the granted option to a certain person, and the law permitted him to amend regarding his legal position and his benefit, and as one of the profit limits, it is kind of the right to choose derived from law to change his legal position"⁽³⁰⁾, for example, the granted permission to the recommended to accept or refuse the will.⁽³¹⁾

Regarding the previous two definitions, it is clear that their creator distinguishes between the capability and the permission, the capability enters in the Right⁽³²⁾, and there is no existence for the Capability before the Right, and the Capability is one of the Right means by its holder⁽³³⁾.

B.1.1 The Ability

It may be derived from the law as many legal applications, and its resources are the agreement like making the contract terminating without need for excuses or Court warning, or as if the two contractors made restricted conditions for the benefit of one of the contractors or others⁽³⁴⁾.

This project considered the power element at the legal Capability, For example, the person that the contract stands to his benefit can make it valid in three months⁽³⁵⁾, he had considered the principle of this period, as stipulated in the 3rd paragraph of the article 136 Iraqi civil status " This period will be valid if the reason due to the shortage of time and reason elimination", and if the reason of cessation because of coercion, illusion or imperiling with deceit.

Regarding the mentioned above, the capability element means that the minor is unable to validate nor breach his contract due to his disqualification or its absence, and the person in charge cannot violate the contract that signed by the minor or validate it just since he informed the time of issuing this contract. The worst thing in contracting, he can't use his capability to breach the contract or validate it, just in case of obligation removal and the same for the illusion, imperiling and aggrieve.

B.1.2 The Compliance

The most common differences between the Capability and the Right, that the Right deals with commitment with others, while the capability means the person compliance to the capability opposition, and he has no ability like the capability holder, he can push it away neither avoiding it, but he is in the submissive and waiting position of, and he has the right to appeal in case of the Capability holder miss-conducting and prove that the capability holder had miss-used it. The one who had violated the contracting commitment has to obey the other party in using the legal selections, and if he wishes to keep going with the contract or terminate or he requests for the obligatory execution, or rise a responsibility contracting claim. Also, the partner if he had a property share will comply with the partner's orders in case of preemption and the same for ceasing the warranty amount, that the money retainer has the right of not paying and many other examples.

B.1.3 The Advantage

The advantage and its concern is the cause in giving the capability, and also is the cause in using it, and all those who given the capability with legal texts their advantages were achieved, and he may have the advantage in refusing, and who insist the legal clearance may receive the advantage from that, or never hold such capability. The law and agreement never decide a choice to anyone just only to protect his legislated advantage in that, and he will decide when this advantage can be true. Does the advantage become true by using the capability on a specific facet? Or By not using it at all?⁽³⁶⁾.

The advantage element can be achieved within the capability characteristic use, it means practicing it in a certain facet or leave it, it is the one that directs the person to select the available choices. For example, the owner in a curiosity action can practice one of the next options, breach the contract, validate the contract, or disregarding instead of his ability, and this silence over-determined time will be as a confirmation to the contract⁽³⁷⁾. He is using one of these options for his benefit, and he will decide whether the advantage is achieved or not.

C. Distinguishing the legal capability as the suspected status

To understand the legal capability completely, we have to determine its zone in order to avoid suspicion with the Freedom and the Right concepts by others, so we have to distinguish between the Capability, the Right and the Freedom as shown hereunder.

C.1 The distinguish between the Legal Capability and the Freedom

Some Jurisprudent went to a settlement between The legal capability and the Freedom⁽³⁸⁾, and others considered the legal capability as a middle status between the Freedom and the Right⁽³⁹⁾. Only one Jurisprudent considered the legal capability as the permission⁽⁴⁰⁾. The description of the legal capability as a middle status was invalid as we confirmed that in all status that the right creates at. And describing it as semi-concrete we don't support this evidence⁽⁴¹⁾, because the legal capability or the permission regarding the words of others cannot be described as rights in the accurate meaning for the word "the right" due to the existence of the essential differences

between the two terminologies. But the capability is an independent status that cannot be named in other names and expressions. On the other hand, the original physical rights are different from the personal right in a basic point related to the general system, this point is the impossibility of agreeing on other types of property rights⁽⁴²⁾.

The freedom and the capability are common at the necessity of respecting by all, and not to be exposed by others. And both are not included of abuse special rules regarding the Jurisprudent's opinion⁽⁴³⁾, even if we don't agree with that. But this association doesn't mean synonymous and essence due to the essential differences as mentioned hereunder:-

- 1- All people are endowed with freedom, which means there is no difference or variation at the positions of Freedom, but the positions are different if it was concerned with the Legal Capability, and the one who endows with it can change his position regarding his own will.
- 2- The legal capability never awards its holder a sufficient number of alternatives, while Freedom awards all people wide options among these alternatives. The alternatives at freedom are indeterminate, while at the legal capability it is limit and previously known⁽⁴⁴⁾. It means that the given privileges to the legal capability are exclusive with certain conditions within the status law regulations, while The Freedom use is unconditioned just with the general system and the general ethics.
- 3- Ath the legal capabilities, there is a reason for inquiry, while at the freedom the options are wide and awarded for all. The ownership freedom is awarded to all people without the need to talk about the cause, while the legal capability that given to the intercessor to take preemption is to own or not requiring it because the last one is a partner in the property, and selling the share to the strangers by the second partners without informing the other partner that he has the right in the common property⁽⁴⁵⁾.
- 4- The legal protection is awarded to both, the freedom bearer and the legal capability. All the people are committed to respecting the position of the freedom bearer and the legal capability, but the position of this protection is different regarding the ownership and the

freedom in ownership. In the case of ownership and what is related to the freedom in ownership, the legal protection stipulates non-interference by others to the freedom bearer during the processing of using his freedom in ownership.

- 5- The freedom never fades away overtime for all people, and they are free in using these freedoms at any time, any place and the way they selected, in one condition never to be against the system and ethics. The awarded legal capabilities may be followed with some private rules in prescription. The use of legal capabilities is in a specific period such as the regulations that are related to gambling and bet, and the capability of the loser to recover what he had lost in one since losing the amount⁽⁴⁶⁾. We can also see the same for the regular inheritance creditors, and the inheritors to chase the inheritance amounts transferred by the inheritors to others to take their rights in full. The law enabled them to chase and follow the sold quantity to anyone and it should be to the inheritors exclusively to meet their rights⁽⁴⁷⁾. The same for the contract validation or violate it⁽⁴⁸⁾.
- 6- The legal capability may be in the act of composing the legal centers, or in the act of using the legal centers, for example, the capability of accepting the ordainment at the obligatory ordainment⁽⁴⁹⁾, the capability can be used before signing the contract, then the obtained right will be created since signing the contract and the ability to terminate it to the unlimited period⁽⁵⁰⁾. One of the contract parties regarding his can end the correlation of this contract according to the law and the freedom, and always it will be at the pre-creation stage⁽⁵¹⁾.
- 7- We don't agree with whom calls for equality between the legal capability and the freedom of the non-existence of despotic in both⁽⁵²⁾, while if that confirmed at the freedom, it is not confirmed at the legal capability. It is possible to imagine of abusive existence in using the legal capability such as using the abusive in breaching the contract and using abusive in accepting the ordainment, and the abusive in using the capability in terminating the contract⁽⁵³⁾. Regarding the mentioned above, the approach between the two concepts; the freedom and the legal capability may be in specific points, it doesn't negate that both are independent in one feature. So, it is clear that the distinguishing criteria between the both

lie in the reason that gives to the legal capability bearer the ability of selection which is not exist at Freedom.

C.2 Distinguishing between the legal capability and the Right

Remarkably, the legal capability is different than the Right essentially, which arises from the legal capability independence than the Right. These difference lie at the hereunder points:

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- 1- If the legal capability and the Right are common in the legal protection based on the legal general principles, but there are separated at the legal protection. Each of the Rights and the legal capability are protected through the individual's commitment, respecting and not confronting others. But at the Right, the legal protection lies at the ownership freedom in using his right without confronted by others. While at the legal capability, the protection relied on the bearer's ability in using the awarded choice, and the bearer has the option to use it against others.
 - 2- The legal capability bearer can influence the legal positions of others, and this position at the capability is called the compliance or the submissive, and he has no power of acceptance or refusal or any other action toward the legal capability's will. The one who uses the right to confront the unfair, he has to commit to this required duty⁽⁵⁴⁾.
 - 3- The relationship at the right represented with dominant. At the personal rights, the relationship between the debtor and the creditor is necessary, while at the real rights the relationship lies in the bearer's dominance on the disputed⁽⁵⁵⁾. But the nature relationship at the legal capability doesn't include the necessity or dominance, but the bearer has the right to use the capability regarding his will, and others have to obey and be responsible for the consequences.
 - 4- The legal capability may lie at the legal center's establishment and may lie at the effects of the legal center's field, while the Right has the legal centers effects.
 - 5- The legal capability agrees with the Right, that both grant their bearers a certain legal feature in the original rights, while at the legal capability it is not original but urgent, additional

and exceptional. The awarded feature to the capability bearer lies in a narrow and limited choice which is opposite to the Right⁽⁵⁶⁾.

- 6- The status in Right represented in the personal rights, and the things at the real rights. While the status at the legal capability is represented in the legal position of others. So, the status of the capability is always legal.
- 7- Executing all the available choices of the legal capability bearer cannot be apart, for example, the obligatory ordainment may be accepted or refused, while at the Right we can imagine division in use. Regarding the personal rights, the creditor has the right to be paid par of debt by the debtor, and at the right of property, the owners can use part of his property or using it or to go on and give some of his powers to others if he wants to receive some benefit from his property⁽⁵⁷⁾.
- 8- It is impossible to suspend the work of legal capability based on conditional stipulation or stop it for a time. The most common at the legal capability it is used for a certain period. This agrees with the transactions stability principle and considering the capability bearer, for example at the use of preemption capability, both the partner and the buyer cannot expose their shares to an unlimited period, while in the right the condition suspension and the addition can be used unless excluded by a text⁽⁵⁸⁾.
- 9- In view of the fact, the legal capability, and its uses relied on the bearer's will, it is not submitted to the prescription system, especially since the legal capability doesn't impose on its bearer to use it. The non-use of it will cause the doubt case, and lack of certainty regarding the position who confronts the capability bearer, and this is against the stability of the transaction. The legal capability is submitted to the abatement system that is characterized by continuity and standing against the prescription.
- 10- The legal capability never transferred through inheritance before using it when it is related to its bearer, and this opposite to the Right.
- 11- The creditors who decided to them the legal ability cannot use it on behalf of the debtors through an indirect claim. The origin of the direct claim means, that the creditor is not able

to use the legal capability owned by the debtor, hence the uses of legal capabilities were abandoned, or regarding the will and the desire and parties benefit⁽⁵⁹⁾. While the debtors concerning the Right, the issue is opposite. Regarding the mentioned, we have explained the essential differences between the Right and the legal capabilities. The essential differences were confirmed between them, and this assures that the legal capability is an independent status than the Right and the Freedom, and the legal capability is essentially and conceptual difference⁽⁶⁰⁾.

7-The legal capability applications

The legal capabilities have many applications in all law branches, whether the general or the private law. But, we concern only with the applications of civil law. These applications can be divided into two parts:

A-The used capabilities at the Real rights

One of the most important capabilities is adhering to the easement rights regarding the law texts in neighboring commitment⁽⁶¹⁾, the capability of adhering to pre-emption, the capability of requesting wealth division, the capabilities of progressing and tracing, the capability of stepping down the debt and the capability of the debtor mortgagee and other applications. In this paper, only two capabilities will be discussed.

A.1 The capability of adhering to pre-emption

The pre-emption is one of the reasons to acquire ownership between the living persons⁽⁶²⁾, and this capability can be used in case of common property existence⁽⁶³⁾, by giving the neighbor the right of owning the property regarding the conditions stipulated in the law, and some other cases⁽⁶⁴⁾. The argument was risen at the legal Jurisprudence at the pre-emption adoption object. This argument appeared widely between the law jurists, then they had divided into two classes, the first one concerns the pre-emption adoption with the concrete right to justify the pre-emption claim at the Real-Estate court, while the second class went to describe it as one of

the personal rights (labeled to the preemptor), that he has no right in inheritance, transferring wealth and the preemptor's debtors have no right to use in the name of preemptor⁽⁶⁵⁾.

Among these contradicted opinions, most Judges and Jurisprudents didn't consider the preemption as a Right⁽⁶⁶⁾. The preemption is one of the reasons to acquire property regarding the law text. We didn't notice any of the Jurisprudents to consider these means⁽⁶⁷⁾. Regarding the previous analysis and the legal texts that are related to the preemption and its definition and the distinguishing between the legal capability and both: the freedom and the right, we can analyze adopt the preemption as follows:-

If we tried to consider preemption as freedom we will confront essential facts such as; preemption is not for all people but it decided to a certain person with its conditions or to certain persons to achieve the required reasons than other like coparcenary. Also, the given options in freedom are wide and unlimited. The decided options to the preemptor lied in owning or not owning the share or the sold property that sold to the buyer and others.

All the people's positions are equal in using freedom, and the other side of this use is not specified or determined, while at the preemption the one who keeps to preemption he will buy the property, which it will be at the position of compliance and submissive. The most common is the use of excessive freedom in a specific period, and this is against the preemption capability which can be determined by the legal texts⁽⁶⁸⁾. Regarding the mentioned above, the differences between preemption and freedom are essential, and the preemption cannot be adopted as a freedom, but preemption is an independent case. The preemption adoptions are a personal and concrete right. We have already explained the essential difference between the legal capability and the Right, and we will try later to do an application to distinguish between preemption and each of the personal rights and the real rights. The legal protection at the real rights stipulates non-interference to the right bearer in using authorities and exploit power against the creditor in paying the debtor's right. Whereas in preemption, the legal protection stipulates non-interference against the preemptor in using the awarded options in taking the preemption or not

depending on his will only. While the legal relationship between the Right bearer and the right, which represented in domination and the personal right to do a certain action from the debtor. While at the preemption, the seller and the buyer are in the state of complete submissive and compliance to the preemptor's single will, it means that the preemptor has the right regarding his will to interfere at the existed legal relationship between the share seller or the buyer of the property.

And the given distinctive feature to the personal right bearer and the real rights bearer is an original feature and not urgent, while at the preemption the original cannot interfere with the relationships of others. And due to some reasons that preemption stands to, the share, the property, and the sold property the capability of the urgent preemption was decided and enabling the preemptor through the exception to own the property regarding the agreed amount. So, preemption is considered as an exceptional personal case from the authority will⁽⁶⁹⁾.

Regarding the real texts reviewing that are related to the real rights, we see the real rights at all civil laws are inclusive whether they are real rights or accessory rights. In these texts, we don't see any trace of preemption, and because these types came exclusively they will be considered as a part of the general system, which means the addition and omission are forbidden. So these rights cannot be considered as real rights or the right that adhere to personality because it is not fixed but fixed for certain persons if they have specific reasons.

After displaying the essential differences, the differences points, and the use of each of the legal capability and the right it is clear that preemption is an independent case. Preemption is a legal capability. We have to mention to her, that the Iraqi Jurisprudent believes that the preemptor has the reason to require the property, and that was confirmed by Dr, Al-Sanhoori⁽⁷⁰⁾, and it has a middle status among the Freedom and the Right. This means, that preemption cannot be adopted unless it is a capability.

In addition to the above, we knew that the legal capability is the person ability through expressing his will to make legal effects determined by the law directly or indirectly which represented in creating, amending or canceling the legal centers without and commitment from the other side or get rid of these traces.

If we compared the status of preemption with this definition, it is clear that the preemptor can express his free will to the private issues among owning the share or property offered for sale, and if he hasn't all these features and conditions the preemption will never achieve.

If the preemptor's desire to use preemption intentionally to own the property or the offered share, the property owner will be transferred to him according to the agreement with the owner of a decision sentenced by the court regarding the agreed amount between the buyer and the seller. By that means, the preemptor creates a legal position to him to own the share or the offered share, it means he interfered with the legal relationship between the buyer and seller through the agreement between the preemptor, the buyer and the seller or by issuing a courthouse decision. The buyer and the seller have no choice just to obey the preemptor's free will, and in this case, the compliance and submissive are achieved, and with that, the buyer and the seller cannot get free from this ability or the given capability to the preemptor. The relationship between the buyer and the seller is controlled through the free of ownership, will domination and the freedom in contracting. The reasons and the conditions that were achieved in preemption and offered property and between the buyer and the seller led to preemption status, and the preemptor enters this status, dominates the situation, and owns the share or the offered property.

Considering the mentioned above, preemption is considered as a legal capability in its real meaning decided to the preemptor. It is not right to be defined as the right and the license⁽⁷¹⁾, but it is better to be defined as "It is a legal capability that gives the preemptor the right of owning the offered for sale property even coercively against the buyer, and paying all price and expenses as stipulated in the law".

A.2 The capability of dividing the common property

The common property or the Coparcenary is considered as an unlikable system and un-economic so the law gave the right to every partner to remove it. Also, the law made the coparcenary as a temporary status never ended⁽⁷²⁾.

The coparcenary can be ended for many reasons such as partners sale, inheritance and preemption. But the most reasons that led to its termination is the division. Coparcenary maybe becomes obligatory based on the law texts or conditions. In case of conditions, the agreement void to stay at the coparcenary more than the allowed period⁽⁷³⁾. In other situations, the original which is the partner in the capital is not forced to stay at the coparcenary but can require its removal and terminate it. But, what is the given power to the partner in requiring division? The answer to this question is "The Iraqi civil law stipulated that each partner has the right for the capital division of the common capital unless he is not obligated to stay at the coparcenary based on the legal text or condition, and regarding the condition, the division shall not be prevented to five years, and if the partners agreed on the coparcenary for a longer time or un-specific period, the agreement will be considered for five years and the staying condition to the partner will be executed even the one came after him⁽⁷⁴⁾. The law even stipulated if the partners never agreed on the division, the partner has the right to attend the court and remove it⁽⁷⁵⁾. Regarding the two article review and the other counter parted articles, we can see the partner at the common property has the right to request division of the common capital if he is not obliged to stay at the partnership regarding the condition or the text, otherwise, he has to stay as a partner and require to divide the capital. So the ability with its conditions is awarded to the partner but not to all people. And requiring division is not considered as a freedom status, it is awarded to the person includes the common property only⁽⁷⁶⁾.

Considering the ability to require division is one of the rights whether it was real-Estate or personal it impossible because the real rights or the accessory rights exclusively belong to the law. From this point, it is impossible to agree on new types. From the other side, the legal

relationship that existed between the right bearer and the target right is represented with domination, and at the real right, it is represented in a certain act by the debtor. While the relationship between the partner at the common property, other partners, and the common capital the partner is not able to dominate the capital and use the given powers to the real right bearer, utilization and act. The partner can reach to his right without any support from the other part as in the personal right. All the partners at the common property have the right of division if they have the desire or not. In case of no agreement, the court will interfere if there is no legal objection to purge the coparcenary regarding the law⁽⁷⁷⁾.

The ability cannot be considered as a right according to the request to divide the common capital. Since the division request is not considered as a Right or Freedom, considering the partner has the right to divide the common property in case of no objection and stays at the property legally he has the right to stay and request the division or stay at the coparcenary. If his choice is to leave the other partners have to obey this desire, otherwise, the court will follow the procedures of purging regarding the request of who wants the division and terminate the common property status.

B. The capabilities used in personal Rights

We can remark the multiplicity of legal capabilities that are given to the creditor in the personal rights field such as adhering to the legal clearance, and the capability of the debtor's purchase on the account of his creditor⁽⁷⁸⁾, regarding the type. In some cases, the capability can give demand and deposit of the fulfillment and the capability of gift stepping down. At this request, three capabilities will be processed; the adherence of clearance, the capability of using the general insurance means, and the capability of gift stepping down as following.

B.1 The capability of adhering to clearance

Clearance is one of the methods to terminate commitment that is equal to fulfillment, and who is a person that clearance may be decided to him? What are the determining powers to him?

What is the nature of given powers? The Iraqi law stipulated that clearance can be made to the less of debts, and it never executed if he adhered to it for a certain advantage⁽⁷⁹⁾.

Since we have reviewed article 7 and the first paragraph of article 409/ Iraqi civil law, it is clear that the optional clearance can be executed in case of two parties come to a settlement. Instead of making clearance for each to fulfill their commitments, the clearance can be made in fewer debts. The legal clearance is different than the optional clearance, and if the conditions achieved and the Judicial request happened from one of the parties, the court has to issue its verdict, and the court cannot admit it unless one of the parties adhered to the advantage through the claim, because the clearance provisions are not from the general system⁽⁸⁰⁾. Since this kind of clearance is decided by the law, the court has no right to issues the sentence and it has to decide about, even the other party (The debtor) that.

he has no benefit from those acts, and he stands unable in front the other part request, and the commitment will be terminated in fewer debts⁽⁸¹⁾. What it has already said, the relationship between the debtor and the creditor is not a requirement as in the personal Right, and the relationship is not represented in domination, it means it is not considered as one of the real rights (The origin and the Accessory) which is identified exclusively by the law. Also, the debtor in this relationship is unable to object and refuse but he has to obey and be submissive regarding the desire and the will of the other party of the relationship. The trace of adhering to this relationship is the clearance acts if the conditions are meet the requirements. Considering that, the role of the court is to reveal the sentence, and to whom the decision was made the capability of adherence to the obligatory legal clearance gives him the right to step down or latch on.

The adherence of the obligatory legal clearance must be considered a legal capability and defined by a law text and available for everyone who has the desire to adhere to it or step down from it. We suggest defining the obligatory legal clearance as " the capability of projection a wanted debt toward his opponent in return of waned debt from that person to his opponent".

B.2 Using the capabilities in the Debtor's Guarantees

However, various capabilities exist at the debtor's guarantees in the indirect claim and the invalidity of acts, we will explain the capability of seizing bankrupted debtor and the capability of detention for a guarantee as showing below:

1. The confinement against the bankrupted Debtor

Since we reviewed all the confinement regulations against the debtor, it is obvious that this requiring is an awarded ability to the creditor which means determination but not release. This ability to a certain person or persons due to their legal positions regarding the relationship with the debtor and is opposite to the freedom. Regarding the relationship nature between the debtor and the creditor in requiring confinement, the creditor has no relation to the court decision issuance through the debtor, And the debtor cannot do any act as in the personal right and execute the conditions, then the court will approve the request to create the confinement decision, then the seizure decision will be issued from the enforcement division toward the seized capital legally if the debtor didn't pay his debts. The court's decision to reserve the public capital⁽⁸²⁾.

Regarding the mentioned above, we can't imagine that there is a dominant relationship between the debtor and the debtors and the capital of the debtor, whether it was before or after the decision. The ability of bankrupted debtor seizure is not considered as a real right. While the debtor concerning the seizure, he has the right of requiring or not requiring, and if he did and required the seizure, that court has to issue the seizure decision. The executive department regarding the issued decision must confine the debtor's wealth, and the debtor has no other solution only to comply and submissive. Considering the issued decision, the creditor has to prevent the debtor from using the given legal powers. If the debtor's wealth is sold legally by the court, all the creditor's rights will be paid. We can see that others have the right to interfere

and control the debtor's wealth to comply with the creditor's desire. So, the creditors have the legal capacity for the debtor's wealth seizure based on the legal texts⁽⁸³⁾.

2. The capability of confinement for Guarantee

The capability of confinement as a personal right or real right is ignored by some entities, and they said that confinement will lead to non-execution and it is one of the special means that had been decided to the creditor⁽⁸⁴⁾.

We agreed on this opinion. The detention cannot be considered as a real right, because it never gives the beneficiary the capability of progress for whom the real and accessory rights were determined, and never gives the capability of traceability for all who received the real rights. The detention does not give the claimant the privilege for his act⁽⁸⁵⁾, and these differences are essential in no way. The detention also cannot be described as a personal right and it is not the liability of the debtor such as the debt which is the debtor's liability in the personal right.

The capability of detention is determined by some creditors in certain cases, and it possible to describe it as a granted freedom to all people. Regarding the mentioned above, the capability detention is not considered as a real or personal or freedom right, even it is right to say what the guarantee means. This capability is one of the legal capabilities determined by the law granted to the creditor if its conditions are never achieved⁽⁸⁶⁾. The debtor according to his status has no way just too submissive and compliant to the decisions made by the creditor if he selected detention or opposite. The detention capability needs no excuses. And the one who has this capability, the wealth bearer has no right to recover and the complaint has the right of delivery objection without any pressures. So, the debtor has no way just to obey and execute his commitments, even he paid part of the required amount, the detention capability will be valid⁽⁸⁷⁾. The effect of this capability can be terminated if the debtor paid all the debt in his liability or the claimant has waived from his right or the creditor used the determined capability in terminating the contract⁽⁸⁸⁾. By the mentioned above, and the capability of detention is not a

right thing or freedom, but it is a legal capability that can be defined as "The granted legal capability given to a person who is related to another person legally or objectively (materially), and has the right to jail the other person if he refused the capital under his liability".

C. The Benefactor's capability in Gift back off

The Iraqi legislator at the Iraqi law stipulated that the benefactor has the right to back off in gift regarding the gifted satisfaction, otherwise the benefactor has the right to back off if there is no reason⁽⁸⁹⁾. After reviewing the article text above, the gift back off regarding the Iraqi civil law can be achieved in two cases:-

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1. The Iraqi legislator permits the gift back off according to the agreement between the Benefactor and the gifted.
 2. If the two parties didn't agree to gift back off, it means the desire of the benefactor without the gifted satisfaction. At this point, the legislator gives the right to the benefactor to back off the gift if two of the below conditions were achieved:

First: An accepted reason achieved.

Second: If there is no reason to back off.

In addition to the mentioned above, the Iraqi civil law stipulated " If the benefactor killed the gifted intentionally without reasonable right, their hires have the right to void the gift"⁽⁹⁰⁾. By Iraqi law, the benefactor has the right to back off the gift if the gifted refused it through the court. This endorsement created by the legislator to give the benefactor a chance if there is a reasonable and accepted purpose by him without any objection by the court to terminate the contract because the court's mission is to reveal the capability of gift back off and it is not a created side.⁽⁹¹⁾

Considering the mentioned above, the gift back off according to cases mentioned above have no right whether it was a personal or real right, but it is a determined legal capability at the personal field through the legislator⁽⁹²⁾. So, we suggest t modulate the text of article 600 of the Iraqi civil

law by saying "The benefactor has the right to back off the gift regarding the gifted satisfaction, and in case of the gifted refusal, the benefactor can retreat in case of reasonable purpose was achieved and no other purpose of backoff is found".

Also, we suggest modulating the text of the article 622/ Iraqi civil law to become "If the gifted killed the benefactor intentionally without any purpose, his hires have the right to void the gift".

From the other side and to achieve justice, the legislator has to determine a certain period and accepted to the benefactor to be able to use the capability of backing off of the gift. Because it is not acceptable that the gifted are exposed along to his life to the issue of gift contract termination, and also for the stability of the transaction⁽⁹³⁾.

8. Conclusion

The conclusion includes the main results and recommendations:

1. The legal capability is considered an obvious out of the Authority will principle, and its practices are considered as an explicit interference at the legal relationships of others.
2. In order not to combine the terminology of freedom with others, we defined it as " a legal option granted to all people to acquire the rights".
3. The legal capability cannot be considered as freedom. The capability is granted to a certain person or persons for certain reasons that do not exist in others. While freedom is granted to all people without any limitation. Regarding that, we can distinguish between capability and freedoms, which means the capability bearer can select among the alternatives.
4. The legal capability cannot be considered as a right from the rights. The Right means a legal commitment to the other side, while the legal capability no one asked about any performance. The relationship between the Right bearer and the other party either a requirement relationship as in the personal right or a domination relationship as in the Real Rights. But the other party in the legal capability is represented in a submissive and compliance position

for the consequence of effects, which is the expression of his will, and never asked for any negative or positive performance.

5. The variant legal capabilities exist in all law branches, but it mostly can be applied at the civil law texts. It may stand on a legal option or stands on the will option.
6. The legal capability is restricted to a certain period. Its approval came to consider the Justice principle in protecting the right bearer, and may he need it to acquire his right from others and law assist him in that. But the transactions stability principle refuses the capability that exists in terms of time and absolute use, so the law calls for period restriction.
7. The capability can be dropped if the determined period is over and never used by its bearer. It can be dropped by waiving or with the act or verbally that contradict later with holding it.
8. The legal capability is mostly used by its bearer, but it may be used for others' benefit, as in the capability of the guardian in refusing the acceptance capability or refusing the debt transfer and so on.

The reasons for capability completion can be seen hereunder:

- A. The determined period completion without starting with it.
- B. Waiver status.
- C. Impossibility of using it.
- D. The capability bearer death, if it's not transferred to hires.

Second: Recommendations

1. We recommend the Iraqi civil law legislator to specify the process of a general text that processes a specific feature to the legal capability's features, conditions of practicing and its types, to enable the researchers to distinguish between the legal capability from one side, and the freedom and the right from the other side.
2. We recommend the Iraqi legislator amend the provisions of the article that are related to the legal capability applications to process the combination problem between the concepts and terminologies by naming these concepts with their names.

3. Since the preemption application is one of the legal capability applications, we recommend amending the article text 1128 of the Iraqi civil law, to be " The preemption is the capability of owning the on-sale property, even it was obligatory to the buyer considering the price and usual costs".
4. Since the legal clearance is one of the legal capability applications, we have defined it as " The capability that allows required debt dropping from his opponent in return for a required debt from that person to his opponent".
5. We recommend defining the detention capability as "A granted legal capability that is related legally or objectively (materially) to another person, and have the right to jail the other person if he refused to pay what in his liability". Also, we recommend the Iraqi legislator in civil codification at the second part/chapter two/ fourth branch to replace the phrase "The right of detention for the guarantee" with "The capability of detention for the guarantee".
6. We recommend amending the text of the article 620/ Iraqi civil law, to be "The benefactor has the right to return in his gift with the gifted satisfaction, if he didn't accept it, the benefactor has the right to change his mind in case of reasonable purpose achieved".
7. We recommend amending the text of the article 622/ Iraqi civil law, and the wording should be " If the benefactor killed the gifted intentionally, his heirs can void the gift".
8. The Iraqi legislator didn't specify a certain period to enable the gifted to use the permitted capability to retreat the gift, and the gifted will be in a risky status of terminating the gift during the whole life of the benefactor. So, we recommend the legislator to identify a certain reasonable period to the benefactor to be able of using the capability of retreating during this period".

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The laws:

1. -Iraqi civil law No:40 for the year 1951.
2. -Egyptian civil law No:131 for the year 1948.

Margins

(1) The legal positions in their wide meaning elaborate human at his surrounded environment regarding his relationships and correlations, for example, the position of each the husband and the wife in the marriage relationship. While the legal positions regarding its limited meaning go to some rights and commitments that lie with the person in his relationships with others. If commitments and rights were dominated we are confronting legal personal positions, while the commitment and assignments are dominated we are confronting subjective legal positions .

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(3) Abu Alail, Ibrahim, Desooqi. Un-necessary contract. A comparative deep study in the Islamic legislation and the status laws. That AL-Salasel press house. 1994,p 187.

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(5) Abbas, Abdul-Hadi. The legal positions and their Appearances at the Syrian Legislation.p257.

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-Al-Bana, Jibraeel. A lesson at the Romanian history and law. Al-Rasheed press house, Baghdad.1934, p255.

(7) This system means the relationship between the man and his maid and wife, and she gave him the right to make children instead of her or the relationship with the maid.

(8) Article 141 from Hammurabi Codex.

(9) The Article 148 of Hammurabi Codex.

(10) Article 142 of Hammurabi codex stipulated that if the wife hated her husband's wife and said " you will not have me" if that was confirmed by the city council and she didn't convict any mistake, and her husband leaving the house too much and devalue her, this woman will not be punished and will leave with all her staff to her father's house.

(11) Hujazi, Abdul-Hay. An Introduction to the legal sciences. The first naming is for Dr. Abdul-Hay Hujazi and the second one is for Dr, Hasan Al-Baghdadi during his presentation to the students at the private law diploma at Alexandria University. Ibid. P118.

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- (13) Taha surah, Verse 58.
- (14) Surqan Surah, Verse 13.
- (15) Qasas Surah, Verse 6.
- (16) Al-Noor Surah, Verse 55.
- (17) Ibn Mandoor. The Arab's Tongue. First edition. Sixth Volume. Beirut. 1997, p 82.
- (18) Ibid
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- (20) Al-Takwir Surah, Verses 21 and 22.
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- (22) Al-Araaf Surah, Verse 10.
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- (25) Same Reference.
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- (31) Citing from Dr. Ibrahim Dsooqi Abu Al-Lail. Previous reference. P178.
- (32) The definition of Dr. Abdullah Mabrook Al-Najjar. Previous reference. P52.
- (33) Ibid.p 45.

- (34) The Iraqi civil status, article 131.
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- ⁽⁷⁸⁾ Remark the Iraqi civil law Article (248).
- ⁽⁷⁹⁾ Iraqi civil law Article (413)
- ⁽⁸⁰⁾ Al-Hakeem, Abdulmajeed. Al-Bakri, Abdul-Baqi. Al-Basheer, Taha, Mohammed. A brief in Iraqi law interpretation. Second part. Commitment provisions. Baghdad University. 1986, p 296.
- ⁽⁸¹⁾ Al-Hakeem, Abdulmajeed. Al-Bakri, Abdul-Baqi. Al-Basheer, Taha, Mohammed. A brief in Iraqi law interpretation. Second part. Commitment provisions. Baghdad University. 1986, p 296.
- ⁽⁸²⁾ Sharaf-Aldean, Ahmed. Commitment Theory. Second part. Commitment regulations. Cairo. 2002. P195.
- ⁽⁸³⁾ Iraqi civil law article 2/271.
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- ⁽⁸⁵⁾ Hujazi, Abdul-Hay. The general theory of commitment regarding the Kuwaiti law. The first part. First folder. Kuwait University.1982,p217.

⁽⁸⁶⁾ Iraqi civil law, Article 2/177.

⁽⁸⁷⁾ Remark the article 1/283 of the Iraqi civil law that counterpart the article text 1/247 of the Egyptian civil law.

⁽⁸⁸⁾ Al-Fadhil , Mundher. Al-Wasit at the civil status law interpretation. Aras press house and publication, Erbil. 2006,0496

⁽⁸⁹⁾ Iraqi civil law, article 620 counter parted with the Egyptian civil law article 500.

⁽⁹⁰⁾ Iraqi civil law, article 621 counter parted with the Egyptian civil law article 2\500.

⁽⁹¹⁾ Iraqi civil law, article 623 counter parted with the Egyptian civil law article 502.

⁽⁹²⁾ Iraqi civil law, article 622 .

⁽⁹³⁾ Abu Alail, Ibrahim, Desooqi. Un-necessary contract. A comparative deep study in the Islamic legislation and the status laws.That AL-Salasel press house. 1994,p 42 and next.